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A Statistical Analysis of the Entrepreneurial Passion and Profitability of Micro-Coffee Shop Owners

Jason Rick T. Suanes,* Merry Rose R. Reyes, Trizie Anne R. Romasanta, Sharmaine H. Matamorosa,
Joaquin Clemente R. Permejo

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Due to the ongoing trend of business owners establishing micro-coffee shops throughout the past few years, this study analyzes the relationship between entrepreneurial passion and profitability through net profit margin (NPM). A survey instrument was administered to 100 micro-coffee shop owners in the Greater Manila Area to test the hypothesis that a significant positive relationship exists between these two variables. Despite owners reporting both high entrepreneurial passion and strong average NPM, the study surprisingly found no significant link between entrepreneurial passion and profitability. Notably, all surveyed owners, despite varying ages and educational backgrounds, had recently founded their businesses within the past five years. Also, a significant difference was found between nascent (1-2 years) and non-nascent (more than 2 years) entrepreneurs in regards to their NPM. Future research through various methodologies may explore the influence of other psychological factors or external variables on profitability and ultimately, business success.

Keywords: *micro-coffee shop owners, entrepreneurial passion, founding, inventing, developing, net profit margin*

Introduction

The allure of coffee transcends its taste, often serving as a social catalyst, a personal comfort, or even as a mere stimulant. Embedded in this cultural phenomenon are the micro-coffee shops that have existed amidst the global coffee boom (Tampon, 2023). These independent businesses, characterized by their intimate settings and personalized service, have captivated customers from different walks of life (Department of Agriculture, 2017). These establishments often operate within neighborhoods, pop-up spaces, or even hole-in-the-wall eateries, contributing to this global phenomenon (Hernisa et al., 2023; Nurhasanah & Dewi, 2020; Teixeira, 2020). Yet, despite their prevalence, limited exploration exists regarding the psychological foundation of its lifeblood—the entrepreneur.

At the heart of these businesses are the individuals driven by a passion for entrepreneurship. It is the entrepreneurial spirit, coupled with a deep-rooted love for their craft that fuels these businesses. Motivated by this trend, this study seeks to understand micro-coffee shop owners, examining the relationship between entrepreneurial passion and profitability. Understanding the psychological foundation of these business owners in terms of entrepreneurial passion can aid the researchers in contributing to the broader understanding of human motivation and behavior in entrepreneurial contexts that would ultimately lead to financial health and entrepreneurial success.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' demographic profile according to:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.3. years of entrepreneurial experience?
2. What is the score on the entrepreneurial passion scale across its different facets based on:
 - 2.1. entrepreneurial passion for inventing;
 - 2.2. entrepreneurial passion for founding; and
 - 2.3. entrepreneurial passion for developing?
3. What is the level of profitability of these micro-coffee shops?
4. Is there a significant difference in the entrepreneurial passion scale scores based on the micro-coffee shop owners' demographic profiles?
5. Is there a significant difference in the profitability index and the micro-coffee shop owners' demographic profiles?
6. Is there a significant relationship between entrepreneurial passion and profitability among micro-coffee shop owners across its different facets?

Literature Review

To formally define entrepreneurial passion, Cardon et al. (2013) focused on developing a reliable and valid measurement tool for assessing entrepreneurial passion in their landmark study called “Measuring entrepreneurial passion: Conceptual foundations and scale validation.” Their study defines entrepreneurial passion as the “consciously accessible intense positive feelings experienced by engagement in entrepreneurial activities associated with roles that are meaningful and salient to the self-identity of the entrepreneur.” They propose a multidimensional framework encompassing three key aspects: passion for inventing, passion for founding, and passion for developing. The research then presents a measurement scale for assessing these three dimensions of entrepreneurial passion.

This study adopts a pragmatic approach to the theoretical underpinnings. While a single, overarching framework is not explicitly employed, the research draws upon relevant concepts from the literature on passion, entrepreneurship, and venture creation to inform the development of the entrepreneurial passion measurement tool. The research employed a survey targeting entrepreneurs and the survey included items designed to capture the three facets of entrepreneurial passion developed by the authors. Statistical analysis was then used to validate the measurement scale and assess its internal consistency and reliability. The study then successfully validates a nine-item scale for measuring entrepreneurial passion, capturing its three proposed dimensions. This provides researchers with a sound tool to assess this important construct in future studies.

This study offers a novel framework for understanding entrepreneurial passion as a multidimensional construct. Moreover, the proponents managed to develop and validate a measurement scale specifically designed to assess this concept, addressing a gap in existing research. This research is crucial for the current study because it provides a means to operationalize and measure entrepreneurial passion, a key variable that will be investigated. By utilizing the scale developed by Cardon et al. (2013), the researchers can effectively assess the level of entrepreneurial passion among micro-coffee shop owners in the Philippines and explore its connection to their business profitability. However, the study focuses on entrepreneurs in general and may not capture the specific nuances of passion experienced by micro-coffee shop owners. In addition, the research relies on self-reported data, which may be susceptible to bias.

From an entrepreneur's point of view, Schulte-Holthaus and Kuckertz (2023) investigated in "How Life Context Affects Entrepreneurs' Passion and Performance" how an entrepreneur's life context influences their passion and business performance. They examine factors like age, gender, family background, and prior work experience to understand their impact on entrepreneurial passion and ultimately, firm performance. This study leverages two theoretical frameworks, namely Person-Environment Fit Theory and Self-Determination Theory. Person-Environment Fit Theory is based on success and well-being depends on how well their characteristics align with the demands and opportunities of their environment. On the other hand,

Self-Determination Theory emphasizes the importance of fulfilling three basic psychological needs for optimal human functioning: autonomy, competence, and relatedness.

The research employed a survey targeting entrepreneurs in a specific geographic location. Statistical analysis was then used to examine the relationships between life context factors, entrepreneurial passion, and business performance. Ultimately, the study found out that Life Context Factors (LCF) do not simply have a positive or negative impact on Entrepreneurial Passion. The study found that LCF can have both positive and negative influences, depending on the specific factors and the entrepreneur's situation. Entrepreneurial passion is not a single, uniform concept. Instead, it is composed of multiple aspects, potentially including both positive and negative emotions and motivations.

This research is relevant to the current study because it explores how factors beyond individual characteristics can influence entrepreneurial passion. By understanding how life context shapes passion, the researchers can gain a more holistic perspective on the experiences of micro-coffee shop owners in the Philippines. The study supports the idea that entrepreneurial passion is not simply a fixed personality trait but can be influenced by various life experiences. This aligns with the possibility that the experiences of micro-coffee shop owners in the Philippines may influence their level of passion and ultimately, their business success. Still, limitations include the generalizability of findings to entrepreneurs in different contexts (e.g., the Philippines) and the potential for self-reported data to be biased.

Aside from individual characteristics, entrepreneurial passion also seems to play a role in a person's behavior. Feng and Chen (2020) in "The Impact of Entrepreneurial Passion on Psychology and Behavior of Entrepreneurs" studied the impact of entrepreneurial passion on the psychology and behavior of entrepreneurs. They examined how different types of passion (i.e. harmonious and compulsive) influence entrepreneurial persistence and ultimately, business performance. The study utilizes Self-Efficacy Theory, which posits that an individual's belief in their capabilities influences their motivation and performance. The study explores how passion fosters self-efficacy, leading to behaviors that drive business success.

The research employs a survey targeting entrepreneurs. The survey may have assessed different types of passion and entrepreneurial behaviors, with statistical analysis used to explore the relationships between these variables. The study finds that compulsive passion, characterized by a strong need to engage in an activity, has a more significant positive impact on persistence and performance than harmonious passion, which is driven by enjoyment. Both types of passion are linked to self-efficacy, which acts as an intermediary factor influencing behavior. This research is relevant to the current study because it delves deeper into the psychology behind entrepreneurial passion. By understanding how passion types influence self-efficacy and behavior, the researchers can gain a more nuanced perspective on the motivations and actions of micro-coffee shop owners in the Philippines.

The study supports the belief that passion is not a single, uniform construct. Different types of passion can have varying influences on an entrepreneur's psychology and behavior. This aligns with the possibility that micro-coffee shop owners in the Philippines might be driven by a mix of enjoyment and a need for control, impacting their business decisions and approach. The research acknowledges limitations in using self-reported data through questionnaires, which can be susceptible to bias. Additionally, the study relies on entrepreneurs' perceptions of their performance, potentially introducing further inaccuracies.

For the main variables, Adomako (2022) examined the relationship between entrepreneurial passion and the profitability of ventures in emerging markets in “Entrepreneurial Passion and Venture Profit: Examining the Moderating Effects of Political Connections and Environmental Dynamism in an Emerging Market.” The study goes beyond a simple linear relationship, exploring two factors that influence how passion translates into profit. First is political connections on whether having it strengthens the positive impact of passion on profitability. Next is environmental dynamism wherein how the level of change and uncertainty in the business environment (e.g., economic fluctuations and new regulations) affects the relationship between passion and profit. This and the current study are directly connected to this study's focus on entrepreneurial passion and profitability, as reinforced by the current study's Mixed Embeddedness Model. The study draws on Cardon's model of Entrepreneurial Passion, which proposes different types of passion and their potential influence on entrepreneurial success.

The research methodology involved data collection from entrepreneurs in an emerging market as well as measures of entrepreneurial passion, political connections, environmental dynamism, and venture profit. Finally, statistical analysis was used to assess the moderating effects of political connections and environmental dynamism on the relationship between passion and profit. The study found that entrepreneurial passion has a positive influence on venture profit and political connections can amplify the positive effect of passion on profit. It was also discovered that in highly dynamic environments, the moderating effect of political connections might be stronger.

This study offers valuable insights by exploring how external factors like political connections and environmental dynamism can influence this relationship applicable to the Philippine context. The research supports the belief that a simple link between passion and profit might be too simplistic. External factors can play a role. It suggests that passion can be a stronger driver of profit when political connections are present and the environment is less dynamic. The study focuses on a different industry (manufacturing) and a specific emerging market (Ghana). Its generalizability to Philippine micro-coffee shops requires further exploration. Additionally, the research does not delve into the specific mechanisms through which political connections and environmental dynamism influence the passion-profitability relationship.

Another existing literature that can give useful insights regarding entrepreneurial passion and profitability is from the book “The Profits and Perils of Passion in Entrepreneurship” by Cardon and Murnieks (2020) as they dove deep into the complex relationship between entrepreneurial passion and its impact on business success. It moves beyond a simplistic view and acknowledges both the potential benefits and drawbacks of passion in the entrepreneurial journey. The theoretical framework draws on concepts from entrepreneurship and psychology. It explores theories related to motivational theories regarding the types of passion (harmonious vs. obsessive) as well as entrepreneurial cognition that pertains to how passion shapes decision-making, risk-taking, and goal pursuit in entrepreneurs.

The book involves a comprehensive review of existing literature on entrepreneurial passion and its outcomes. It integrated findings from various research methods used in prior studies, such as surveys, interviews, and case studies of entrepreneurs. The authors highlighted that the relationship between passion and profitability is not always straightforward. Harmonious passion (driven by enjoyment and challenge) can be beneficial, leading to increased effort, persistence, and ultimately, higher profitability. On the other hand, obsessive passion (characterized by a compulsive drive for success) can have both positive and negative effects. While it can fuel hard work and dedication, it can also lead to burnout, unhealthy risk-taking, and hinder profitability.

This book provides a foundational understanding of this complex relationship, allowing the researchers to explore the potential benefits and drawbacks of passion within the specific context of Philippine micro-coffee shop owners. The research supports the concept that passion for one's business can be a double-edged sword for entrepreneurs. While it can be a powerful motivator, understanding the different types of passion and their potential consequences is crucial. It is important to remember that this book offers a broad overview. It might not delve into the specific ways passion manifests within different industries like coffee shops. Additionally, it does not explore the moderating factors that can influence the passion-profitability relationship in the current study's context.

Lastly, this research by Aulia et al. (2021) entitled “The Effect of Entrepreneurial Characteristics on Entrepreneurial Competence and Entrepreneurial Competence on Business Performance of Micro and Small-Scale Coffee Shops in Bogor, Baskara” explored the relationship between entrepreneurial characteristics, entrepreneurial competence, and business performance in micro and small-scale coffee shops located in Bogor, Indonesia. Although not directly measured in this study, the focus on entrepreneurial characteristics provides valuable insights that may be indirectly related to passion. Specific characteristics, such as opportunity recognition and innovation, could potentially be linked to the passionate pursuit of a coffee shop venture. To further explore this potential connection, the study draws upon two existing models. The first model, titled “The Model of Entrepreneurial Competence, Environmental Factors, and Business Performance,” investigates how various entrepreneurial characteristics influence an entrepreneur's competence, which in turn impacts business performance. The second model, “The Model of Entrepreneurial Performance,” delves deeper into the multifaceted nature of entrepreneurial success by examining the diverse factors that contribute to it.

The research methodology involved surveys being distributed to micro and small-scale coffee shop owners in Bogor to assess their entrepreneurial characteristics and business performance. Statistical analysis was used to identify correlations between these factors and entrepreneurial competence. The study found that entrepreneurial characteristics significantly influenced entrepreneurial competence, particularly for micro-scale coffee shops. Psychological characteristics only impacted competence in small-scale shops, not micro-scale. Additionally, entrepreneurial competence significantly influenced business performance for both micro and small-

scale coffee shops. By examining the link between entrepreneurial characteristics, competence, and performance in a similar business setting, it sheds light on factors influencing profitability, even if passion is not directly addressed. The research supports the notion that entrepreneurial characteristics play a crucial role in the success of micro and small-scale coffee shops. This aligns with the idea that certain owner traits and skills can contribute to profitability. The study focuses on a specific location (Bogor, Indonesia) and might not be generalizable to the Philippines. Additionally, it does not directly explore the role of passion. Finally, the reference mentions limitations like sample size and the need for further research during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a quantitative approach to explore the relationship between entrepreneurial passion and profitability among micro-coffee shop owners. Data were collected using survey questionnaires, enabling efficient data gathering from a large sample. This helps facilitate statistical analysis to identify significant correlations and relationships (Mohajan, 2020). Specifically, a correlational research design was used to examine the association between entrepreneurial passion and profitability, measured by Net Profit Margin (NPM). This design allowed for the determination of both the strength and direction of this relationship (Duckett, 2021).

Respondents

This study focused on owners of independent micro-coffee shops in the Greater Manila Area. They were recruited through purposive sampling, involving direct contact with coffee shops via personal visits and online channels. Owners meeting the inclusion criteria (independent ownership and operation for at least one year) were invited to participate. Purposive sampling ensures the sample represents the target population, enhancing the generalizability of findings (Andrade, 2020).

One hundred owners of independent micro-coffee shops in the Greater Manila Area were selected. This sample size is appropriate for a correlational study (Fox, 2024; Kaya, 2020), exceeding the recommended minimum of 30. Franchises were excluded due to their pre-defined business models, which could obscure the unique experiences and decision-making of independent owners (Siebert, 2024). On the other hand, one-year operational requirement ensured business stability and allowed for the capture of data reflecting a more sustainable business model. This inclusion criteria addressed the potential for inaccurate profit representation during initial investment periods (Barlow, 2023; Malaluan, 2019) and focused the study on owners with at least a baseline level of entrepreneurial experience, enabling exploration of passion's role in profitable ventures.

Participants included both nascent (1-2 years of experience) and non-nascent (more than 2 years) entrepreneurs (Kişi, 2020). Age groups were categorized as 18-30, 31-45, 46-60, and 61+, aligning with the framework established by Vesalainen and Pihkala (2000) for identifying key stages in entrepreneurial identity development.

Instrument

Entrepreneurial passion among micro-coffee shop owners was measured using Cardon et al.'s (2013) Entrepreneurial Passion Scale. This validated instrument assesses passion across three domains: inventing, founding, and developing. Consistent with Cardon et al.'s (2013) recommendations, a 7-point Likert scale was used to avoid range restriction. The scale demonstrated strong internal consistency, with reliability coefficients exceeding .70 for all three domains (Cardon et al., 2013). This confirms that each domain consistently measured its respective aspect of entrepreneurial passion. Construct validity was supported by high correlations between the passion domains and their corresponding dimensions, indicating that passion for different entrepreneurial activities are distinct constructs (Cardon et al., 2013). Domain scores for entrepreneurial passion were calculated by multiplying the average intensity of positive feelings score by the identity centrality score.

Profitability was assessed quantitatively using net profit margin (NPM). It is defined as a profitability ratio calculated by dividing net income by net revenue. NPM is a crucial metric for assessing a business's financial health. A higher NPM signifies superior economic performance as it reflects the percentage of revenue converted into profit after accounting for all expenses (Choiriyah et al., 2021). Hence, sections for putting net income and net revenue were added to the instrument.

The instrument also included a section for collecting demographic information. Before the main study, a pilot test was conducted with a small sample of micro-coffee shop owners to ensure the instrument's clarity, psychometric soundness, and feasibility for the target population. The pilot study demonstrated robust reliability across all measures, as evidenced by high Cronbach's α , McDonald's ω , and item-total correlations.

Procedure

Prior to commencing full-scale data collection, a pilot test was conducted to refine the research instrument, data collection procedures, and overall study design. Data from the pilot test were entered into a secure spreadsheet with the purpose of enhancing data quality and the reliability of subsequent findings. Following these refinements, the main data collection phase began.

Potential respondents, meeting pre-defined inclusion criteria, were identified through online directories, social media platforms, and direct engagement with coffee shop owners. This direct engagement involved both on-site visits and online inquiries to coffee shops

within the selected cities. After explaining the research project, informed consent was obtained from participating owners before proceeding with quantitative data collection. The collected data were then subjected to statistical analysis to determine the relationships between the key variables.

Data Analysis

Following manual entry into a secure spreadsheet, all survey data underwent rigorous review and cleaning to ensure accuracy and completeness. Statistical analysis was performed using specialized software. Given the sample size exceeding 50, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was employed to assess normality (Demir, 2022). Descriptive statistics, including weighted means for entrepreneurial passion scores and net profit margin, were calculated to summarize key variables. Frequency tables further facilitated data organization.

To explore potential relationships between demographic profiles and the study's main variables, non-parametric tests were selected due to the data's non-normal distribution. Specifically, the Mann-Whitney U test was used for comparisons between two groups, while the Kruskal-Wallis test was applied for comparisons involving more than three groups (Okoye & Hosseini, 2024b). The strength and direction of the relationship between entrepreneurial passion and net profit margin were then assessed using Spearman's rho, a suitable approach for non-normally distributed data (Okoye & Hosseini, 2024a).

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Demographic Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Age		
18-30 years old	61	61
31-45 years old	33	33
46-60 years old	5	5
61+ years old	1	1
Highest Educational Attainment		
College	63	63
College Undergraduate	17	17
Graduate School	12	12
High School (Old Curriculum)	5	5
Senior High School	2	2
Elementary	1	1
Years of Entrepreneurial Experience		
1-2 Years (Nascent)	64	64
3-5 Years (Non-Nascent)	36	36

Table 1 highlights that 61% of the respondents are 18-30-year-old micro-coffee shop owners, whereas 33% are 31-45 years old, 5% are 46-60 years old, and 1% are 61% years old. These findings are consistent with the study of Aulia et al. (2021) which indicates that young adults dominate the micro-coffee shop scene in Bogor, Indonesia. This implies that owners of this age exhibit high motivation levels, a strong need for accomplishment, and a cosmopolitan outlook, albeit with relatively limited professional experience.

This is also consistent with the findings of Cada (2022), which states that young adult Filipinos view the country as a promising environment for entrepreneurial ventures. This is fueled by the Philippine government's steps to encourage entrepreneurship by enacting the Young Entrepreneurship Act (Republic Act No. 10679) alongside various private organizations that actively offer programs to support aspiring entrepreneurs.

The findings also show that the majority of respondents are college graduates. A significant portion, 17%, are college undergraduates. Additionally, 12% have completed graduate school, 5% are high school graduates from the older curriculum, 2% are Senior High School graduates, and a small percentage, 1%, have only finished elementary school. This is congruent with the local study by Simon and Suarez (2022), which found that college graduates comprise most MSMEs either as owners or managers. This phenomenon is best explained by the findings of Kadiyono et al. (2019), who indicate that entrepreneurial graduates exhibit higher self-confidence, optimism, and resilience levels. They are better equipped to set and achieve goals, making them more successful in entrepreneurial endeavors. Conversely, Aulia et al. (2021) found that most micro-business owners are elementary school graduates, suggesting that limited access to resources, rather than a lack of interest in skill development, may contribute to lower educational attainment in this sector.

Lastly, the results indicate that 64% of the respondents are nascent entrepreneurs with 1-2 years of experience, while the remaining 36% are non-nascent with 3-5 years of experience. Despite this difference, the overall trend is clear: a significant growth in micro-coffee shops over the past five years. This aligns with the projections outlined in the Department of Agriculture's 2017-2022 roadmap. The coffee industry's surge has encouraged many Filipino entrepreneurs to start micro-coffee businesses, often combining various resources to create innovative ventures. Francisco (2023) found that these nascent entrepreneurs are motivated by the opportunity to provide in-demand services and make a positive impact. The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated this trend.

Table 2.1. *Entrepreneurial Passion for Inventing Scores*

	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
It is exciting to figure out new ways to solve unmet market needs that can be commercialized.	6.46	.81	Strongly Agree
Searching for new ideas for products/services to offer is enjoyable to me.	6.67	.57	Strongly Agree
I am motivated to figure out how to make existing products/services better.	6.78	.50	Strongly Agree
Scanning the environment for new opportunities really excites me.	6.60	.72	Strongly Agree
Inventing new solutions to problems is an important part of who I am.*	6.61	.63	Strongly Agree
Overall Domain Average Score	43.99	6.41	Above Average EP Levels

Note. $n=100$

Note. Item/s with asterisk (*) = Identity Centrality (IC); Item/s without asterisk (*) = Intense Positive Feelings (IPF)

Note. EP levels are interpreted based on established norms done through pilot testing. Overall domain average score for EP-Inventing in the normative data is 35.59

Table 2.1 shows that most respondents strongly agree with the statements about entrepreneurial passion for inventing the domain, with an overall average score of 43.99. It also indicated above-average levels of entrepreneurial passion when compared with the normative data. Solomon and Mathias (2020) noted that entrepreneurs from different sectors with a high entrepreneurial passion for inventing prioritize artistic expression and personal satisfaction over rapid growth and scaling. This implies passion for the creative and inventive process and a desire to maintain autonomy, which is often associated with the entrepreneurial drive of inventing. Additionally, even though micro-businesses often have limited resources and a narrow range of products, they constantly innovate due to the entrepreneur's motivations (Tugade, 2020). This allows them to exploit external factors like market demand, profitability, and economic opportunities.

One major factor that also influences entrepreneurial passion for inventing is due to the COVID-19 Pandemic. Widani et al. 's (2022) study revealed that creating new product variants can indirectly attract new customers and determine market opportunities. Ultimately, the pandemic has accelerated the need for innovation and creativity, pushing entrepreneurs to think outside the box and invent solutions to minimize challenges and maximize opportunities (Ardiansyah et al., 2019). This trend will likely continue as entrepreneurs harness the power of innovation to shape a more resilient and sustainable future.

Table 2.2. *Entrepreneurial Passion for Founding Scores*

	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Establishing a new company excites me.	6.13	1.29	Agree
Owning my own company energizes me.	6.58	.81	Strongly Agree
Nurturing a new business through its emerging success is enjoyable.	6.57	.95	Strongly Agree
Being the founder of a business is an important part of who I am.*	6.47	1.05	Strongly Agree
Overall Domain Average Score	42.28	9.99	Above Average EP Levels

Note. $n=100$

Note. Item/s with asterisk (*) = Identity Centrality (IC); Item/s without asterisk (*) = Intense Positive Feelings (IPF)

Note. EP levels are interpreted based on established norms done through pilot testing. Overall domain average score for EP-Founding in the normative data is 40.

Table 2.2 also shows that most respondents displayed a level of agreement and above-average entrepreneurial passion for founding, with a domain average score of 42.48. This is different from Cardon et al.'s (2017, as cited in Kumari, 2023) findings, that entrepreneurs are often passionate about micro-business creation and growth but not about founding. One potential explanation for this lack of enthusiasm is that starting a business is often seen as a risky endeavor with risky activities (Saif & Ghanian, 2019).

Despite this expectation, respondents demonstrated strong agreement with the domain, expressing high levels of passion for the venture creation process and exhibiting entrepreneurial personality traits (Walsh & Cunningham, 2023). Hence, the perceived risks and challenges associated with founding are outweighed by the satisfaction of building something new. These micro-coffee shop owners are passionate about innovation and business growth. They actively seek out new approaches to conducting business and are highly motivated to succeed as entrepreneurs (Kusa & Danladi, 2024).

Additionally, Table 2.3 reveals that all respondents strongly agreed with the importance of entrepreneurial passion for development, with a mean of 43.51, particularly displaying an above-average entrepreneurial passion level. According to Luu and Nguyen (2020), this passion can lead to ambitious expectations for business success. As a result, entrepreneurs are more likely to explore new ideas

rather than relying on existing strategies. This innovative mindset can significantly contribute to improved business performance. Entrepreneurial passion, especially when coupled with self-discipline and perseverance, can boost performance and foster a stronger entrepreneurial mindset. Crucially, opportunity alertness plays a key role in mediating this positive relationship (Lee & Herrmann, 2019).

Table 2.3. *Entrepreneurial Passion for Developing Scores*

	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I really like finding the right people to market my product/service to.	6.68	.72	Strongly Agree
Assembling the right people to work for my business is exciting.	6.47	.86	Strongly Agree
Pushing my employees and myself to make our company better motivates me.	6.62	.72	Strongly Agree
Nurturing and growing companies is an important part of who I am.*	6.53	1.09	Strongly Agree
Overall Domain Average Score	43.51	9.07	Above Average EP Levels

Note. $n=100$

Note. Item/s with asterisk (*) = Identity Centrality (IC); Item/s without asterisk (*) = Intense Positive Feelings (IPF)

Note. EP levels are interpreted based on established norms done through pilot testing. Overall domain average score for EP-Developing in the normative data is 39.17.

Xiao et al. (2019) found that employees with diverse skills are more likely to form teams, especially when they also have an entrepreneurial passion for developing. Newman et al. (2019) also noted in a literature review that passion for developing seems more closely tied to venture growth and performance. While it may not directly impact persistence, it can drive goal commitment and lead to sustained growth. This means that while passion for inventing and founding may be crucial for the initial stages of entrepreneurship, passion for developing is essential for long-term success. While measured separately, the respondents' scores on all entrepreneurial passion domains reveal they agree to exhibit entrepreneurial passion toward their micro-coffee shops. The average domain scores indicate that these entrepreneurs possess significantly higher levels of entrepreneurial passion than the norm. This unique quality positions them as individuals who thrive on innovation as they actively seek growth opportunities. This is a recipe for long-term success in a dynamic and competitive environment post-COVID-19.

Table 3. *Financial Metrics for Net Profit Margin (NPM) Profitability Index*

	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Monthly Revenue	₱159,461	₱80,000	₱3,000	₱2,800,000
Monthly Expenses	₱107,315	₱50,000	₱1,000	₱2,200,000
Monthly Net Profit	₱52,146.50	₱30,000	₱-3,000	₱600,000
Monthly Net Profit Margin	.40 (40%)	.21 (21%)	-.50 (-50%)	.96 (96%)

Table 3 reports that the mean for the NPM is at 40%, with 96% as the highest NPM and -50% as the lowest. The NPM is a key profitability indicator among micro-coffee shops as changes influence both their earnings and sales. In a study conducted by Victor et al. (2023) among micro-businesses, NPM is closely tied to retained earnings and personal savings, as the returns from these sources depend on the profits generated by the micro-business. An NPM of 7%-10% is often considered a decent benchmark for many businesses. A higher margin, particularly 20% or more, is a strong financial position. On the other hand, a margin below 5% is generally considered low and may signal potential financial instability and difficulty sustaining operations (Munro, 2024; Parker et al. 2024).

The mean NPM displays a positive 40%, signifying an above-average profitability index among micro-coffee shops in Greater Manila. However, the impact of net profit margin on earnings growth is still a subject of debate among researchers. Conflicting findings exist regarding the relationship between these variables, with some studies reporting a significant relationship, while others indicate none suggesting a complex interplay of influencing factors (Handayani & Winarningsih, 2020). A higher NPM indicates a company's ability to convert sales into net income more efficiently (Yang & Zhang, 2020). This suggests better operational and financial management among the respondents.

Table 4 reveals no significant difference between age and the different domains of entrepreneurial passion, with all having a p-value of more than 0.05. This is congruent with the findings of Bignetti et al. (2021) that there is no significant difference between the two age groups (17-23 years old and 23 years old and above) involved in their study in terms of entrepreneurial passion and entrepreneurial intention. A possible explanation for this is that different age groups do not differ when it comes to motivating individuals to innovate and initiate the process of starting a business.

Table 4. Significant Difference in Entrepreneurial Passion Scores According to the Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variables Tested	<i>p</i>	Decision	Interpretation	
Age	EP - Inventing	.602	Failed to reject H ₁	No significant difference
	EP - Founding	.682	Failed to reject H ₂	No significant difference
	EP - Developing	.984	Failed to reject H ₃	No significant difference
Highest Educational Attainment	EP - Inventing	.261	Failed to reject H ₄	No significant difference
	EP - Founding	.386	Failed to reject H ₅	No significant difference
	EP - Developing	.302	Failed to reject H ₆	No significant difference
Years of Entrepreneurial Experience	EP - Inventing	.188	Failed to reject H ₇	No significant difference
	EP - Founding	.672	Failed to reject H ₈	No significant difference
	EP - Developing	.290	Failed to reject H ₉	No significant difference

Note. Reject H₀ if the *p*-value is less than or equal to alpha (0.05).

Note. Nascent Entrepreneurs (1-2 Years of Entrepreneurial Experience); Non-Nascent Entrepreneurs (More than 2 Years of Entrepreneurial Experience)

Unlike Huss (2020), who found a small but significant difference in all entrepreneurial passion domains between younger (19-44) and older (45-72) age groups, this study found no such distinction. It suggests differences in how different entrepreneurs, regardless of age, experience passion. Younger entrepreneurs are more receptive to new ideas and methods, while older entrepreneurs are believed to possess greater human, social, and financial capital (Azoulay et al., 2020). Experienced entrepreneurs have advantages due to their accumulated experience, developed skills, expanded networks, and financial resources, which enable them to take on greater risks with a safety net. Younger entrepreneurs, on the other hand, have less time to develop these attributes. While the current study's findings indicate no significant difference in entrepreneurial passion across various age groups, it suggests that the experience of passion among entrepreneurs may be more nuanced than simply being influenced by age. Instead, factors like entrepreneurial propensity may play a more significant role in shaping passion levels.

The findings also report that the highest educational attainment has no significant difference in all entrepreneurial passion domains, all with a *p*-value of more than 0.05. This finding aligns with Kozlinska and Aston University's (2016) research, which, based on a sample of over 500 graduates, demonstrated no significant difference in student outcomes between traditional academic programs and those emphasizing experiential, "learning-by-doing" methodologies. The study characterizes entrepreneurs as people with creativity, strong self-belief, resilience to setbacks, and high entrepreneurial passion. This is anchored by Tenorio-Mandane's (2020) local study, where the highest educational attainment showed no significant difference among entrepreneurial passion-related traits such as personal and cognitive entrepreneurial traits.

In contrast, Msosa (2023) and Lee et al. (2021) reported significant relationships between education and entrepreneurial behavior and passion, respectively. Results revealed that students who took an entrepreneurship class exhibited significantly higher levels of founding passion, intensive positive feelings towards founding, and founding identity centrality than those who did not. While both studies suggest that education can broaden a person's perspective and opportunities, it doesn't necessarily determine their passion for starting a business to pursue these opportunities.

Lastly, results state that nascent and non-nascent entrepreneurs show no significant difference in all domains of entrepreneurial passion. These results resemble Tenorio-Mandane's (2020) local study, in which years of experience bear no significant difference in entrepreneurial passion-related traits. However, most studies indicate that years of entrepreneurial experience significantly affect entrepreneurial passion. Neal (2020) indicates that the results of the analysis indicate that nascent and non-nascent entrepreneurs exhibit different levels of entrepreneurial passion. The study found significant differences in entrepreneurial passion between expert and novice entrepreneurs.

This aligns with previous research suggesting that both differ in various aspects, including decision-making. Non-nascent or expert entrepreneurs tend to exhibit higher levels of passion than nascent or novice entrepreneurs (Wiltbank et al., 2009; Sarasvathy, 2008, as cited in Neal, 2020). This contradicts the group's descriptive findings that nascent entrepreneurs exhibit a higher level of agreement when demonstrating entrepreneurial passion in all domains. This is evident in all domains of entrepreneurial passion, although correlations with other variables need to be considered.

Even with this contradictory result, both nascent and non-nascent entrepreneurs demonstrate a level of entrepreneurial passion that has been linked to positive outcomes, creativity, and long-term business sustainability (Mayoshe & Nuringsih, 2021). Therefore, cultivating passion is crucial for aspiring entrepreneurs to achieve success. Ultimately, findings in the current study display that there is no

significant difference when it comes to the respondents' demographic profiles. Some studies support these claims, while some indicate the contrary. This highlights the complex nature of entrepreneurial passion in the context of micro-coffee shops.

Table 5. *Significant Difference of Net Profit Margin Profitability Index According to the Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

Variables Tested	<i>p</i>	Decision	Interpretation
Age	.414	Failed to reject H_{10}	No significant difference
Highest Educational Attainment	.581	Failed to reject H_{11}	No significant difference
Years of Entrepreneurial Experience	.046	Rejected H_{12}	There is a significant difference

Note. Reject H_0 if the *p*-value is less than or equal to alpha (0.05).

Note. Nascent Entrepreneurs (1-2 Years of Entrepreneurial Experience); Non-Nascent Entrepreneurs (More than 2 Years of Entrepreneurial Experience)

Table 5 indicates that the entrepreneur's age and highest educational attainment have no significant difference on a micro-coffee shop's NPM. This is evident in the studies conducted by Alene (2020) and Yeh et al. (2021). These studies found no statistically significant difference or relationship between age and a business's financial and firm performance. On the contrary, most studies point out that there is a significant difference between an entrepreneur's highest educational attainment (Bayar et al., 2022; Ewing Marion Kauffman Foundation, 2019). However, it is important to note that the businesses involved in this study are micro-coffee shop businesses, which are currently experiencing a global boom in generating profits (Tampon, 2023). Therefore, consumers would continue to patronize micro-coffee shops despite the demographic profile of the micro-coffee shop owner.

However, it showed that years of entrepreneurial experience significantly differ in generating NPM. This is congruent with the study of Nariswari and Nugraha (2020) where NPM has a statistical significance in a business' growth as it ages and as the entrepreneur accumulates experience. This reflects the results in the group descriptive result where the mean NPM of the non-nascent entrepreneurs is an additional 10% over the nascent entrepreneurs. Ogundana et al. (2021) also noted that in a developing country with multiple minority sectors, a business would perform well if the entrepreneur has experience compared to new entrepreneurs, indicating a gap between nascent and non-nascent entrepreneurs. This applies to the current study setting, a developing country with multiple minority sectors (Hansson & Weiss, 2023; Mendoza & Tadeo, 2023). Nevertheless, this goes to show that the NPM varies depending on an owner's years of entrepreneurial experience.

Table 6. *Entrepreneurial Passion and Net Profit Margin Profitability Index Correlation Results*

Variables Tested	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	Interpretation	<i>p</i>	Decision	Interpretation
EP - Inventing	-.05	.0016	Weak Negative Relationship	.638	Failed to reject H_{13}	No significant relationship
EP - Founding	.14	.0196	Weak Positive Relationship	.155	Failed to reject H_{14}	No significant relationship
EP - Developing	-.01	.0001	Weak Negative Relationship	.892	Failed to reject H_{15}	No significant relationship

Note. Reject H_0 if the *p*-value is less than or equal to alpha (0.05).

Table 6 reveals that NPM and entrepreneurial passion for inventing and developing have a weak negative relationship. This implies an inverse relationship between these variables but to a weak extent. With a coefficient of determination of .0016 (.16%) and .0001 (.01%), this implies that the NPM profitability index is the least of the factors that should be considered in assessing entrepreneurial passion relationships. This is also strengthened by the hypothesis testing result that there is no significant relationship between the variables. Additionally, NPM and entrepreneurial passion for founding have a positive but insignificant relationship with a .0196 (1.96%) coefficient of determination.

This study aimed to examine the relationship between entrepreneurial passion and profitability as measured by NPM. By following this research objective following the results of the study, this study is congruent with the book of Cardon and Murnieks (2020), where they found that there is currently a lack of empirical evidence to definitively state that entrepreneurial passion is essential or sufficient for financial success. Hence, rigorous research is needed to isolate the specific impact of passion, controlling for other significant factors like idea quality, market potential, and other entrepreneurial constructs. While entrepreneurial passion is crucial, it is often just the starting point. Other essential psychological factors are needed to build a strong connection between passion and business success, ultimately leading to profit and financial stability (Azzaakiyyah, 2023). Another possible explanation for the lack of relationship between the variables is that while some people are motivated to become entrepreneurs by their passion, others may be driven by

necessity due to limited job opportunities (Cardon & Murnieks, 2020). Additionally, some individuals may identify profitable opportunities and possess the resources to capitalize on them, leading to significant financial success, which explains the high NPM results outlined in Table 6.

On the contrary, entrepreneurial passion is also shown to have a significant relationship with profitability. Instead of employing a direct measure of profitability metric, it used a survey instrument to gauge the profitability of a business venture, ranging from item tackling profit margin, return on investment, and growth in profit levels. However, profitability was assessed using only a three-item scale ($\alpha=0.93$) developed from past studies, adjusted to highlight the profitability of the main business. Results from this study showed that entrepreneurial passion is related to and positively affects not only individual and interpersonal factors but also organizational outcomes (Adomako et al., 2022). This extends the understanding of entrepreneurial passion theory by showing its significant impact on a business's financial performance. Therefore, while entrepreneurial passion is crucial in the entrepreneurial journey, its relationship with financial performance is complex. Further research is needed to fully understand the interplay between passion, other entrepreneurial factors, and business success.

Conclusions

This study investigated the relationship between entrepreneurial passion and profitability, measured by net profit margin.

The following section contains the conclusions drawn from the study:

First, the typical micro-coffee shop owner is a young adult (18-30) with at least some college education, though experience levels vary, with both nascent and seasoned entrepreneurs represented.

Second, owners generally perceive themselves as highly passionate across all three entrepreneurial domains (inventing, founding, and developing), as evidenced by above-average scores.

Third, micro-coffee shops demonstrate substantial profitability, averaging a 40% profit margin, likely driven by current market trends.

Fourth, entrepreneurial passion, while prevalent, appears independent of age, education, and experience among this group, suggesting it is a common trait among micro-coffee shop entrepreneurs.

Fifth, years of entrepreneurial experience significantly influences profitability, with non-nascent entrepreneurs exhibiting higher profitability than their nascent counterparts.

Finally, no significant relationship emerged between entrepreneurial passion and profitability (NPM), indicating that other factors likely contribute more substantially to business success.

The following are the proposed recommendations by the researchers in light of the study's results:

First, employing diverse profitability metrics beyond NPM is recommended. Relying solely on monthly NPM may not fully capture a business's financial health, particularly given potential seasonal fluctuations or one-time events. Exploring alternative measures of business success would provide a more eclectic assessment.

Second, future studies could benefit from statistical techniques like regression analysis to control for confounding variables and enhance the understanding of the relationship between entrepreneurial passion and profitability.

Third, a qualitative approach is warranted to explore the lived experiences and subjective viewpoints of micro-coffee shop owners regarding entrepreneurial passion and profitability, providing richer insights into this complex phenomenon.

Fourth, replicating this study in different geographical contexts with larger sample sizes would help generalize the findings and allow for comparisons across regions.

Fifth, micro-coffee shop owners should balance passion with a pragmatic understanding of external factors impacting profitability. Analyzing market trends, competitor activity, and local economic conditions is essential for informed strategic decisions.

Finally, investigating potential mediating and moderating variables between entrepreneurial passion and profitability, as well as exploring this relationship within other micro-business sectors, could further reveal the dynamics of these constructs and their impact on business outcomes.

References

Adomako, S., Mole, K., Franklin, R. J., & Murnieks, C. Y. (2022). Entrepreneurial passion and venture profit: Examining the moderating effects of political connections and environmental dynamism in an emerging market. *International Small Business Journal*, 41(2), 204–232. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02662426221085182>

Alene, E. T. (2020). Determinants that influence the performance of women entrepreneurs in micro and small enterprises in Ethiopia. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-020-00132-6>

- Andrade, C. (2020). The inconvenient truth about convenience and purposive samples. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 43(1), 86–88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0253717620977000>
- Ardiansyah, M., Wijayanti, R., & Sudjatno. (2019). THE EFFECT OF STRATEGIC PLANNING AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF COFFEE SHOP BUSINESS THROUGH INNOVATION AS INTERVENING VARIABLE. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*, 25(1). https://www.ijbel.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/IJBEL25.ISU-1_128.pdf
- Aulia, M. R., Saragi, C. P., & Simbolon, R. (2021). The effect of entrepreneurial characteristics on entrepreneurial competence and entrepreneurial competence on business performance of Micro and Small-Scale coffee shops in Bogor. *Baskara*, 4(1), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.54268/baskara.4.1.37-48>
- Azoulay, P., Jones, B. F., Kim, J. D., & Miranda, J. (2020). Age and High-Growth Entrepreneurship. *American Economic Review Insights*, 2(1), 65–82. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aeri.20180582>
- Azzaakiyyah, H. K. (2023). An Entrepreneur's Character from Professor Musa Asy'arie's Perspective. *Apollo: Journal of Tourism and Business*, 1(1). <https://journal.mediadigitalpublikasi.com/index.php/apollo/article/view/7/7>
- Barlow, T. (2023, October 6). How much does a coffee shop make? A concise analysis. *Majesty Coffee*. <https://majestycoffee.com/blogs/posts/how-much-does-a-coffee-shop-make-a-concise-analysis#:~:>
- Bayar, Y., Sart, G., Gavriletea, M. D., & Coroş, M. M. (2022). THE IMPACT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION AND EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT ON ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY: EVIDENCE FROM SELECTED HIGH-INCOME ECONOMIES. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 23(6), 1257–1279. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jbem.2022.17840>
- Bignetti, B., Santos, A. C. M. Z., Hansen, P. B., & Henriqson, E. (2021). THE INFLUENCE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL PASSION AND CREATIVITY ON ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS. *RAM. Revista De Administração Mackenzie*, 22(2). <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-6971/eramr210082>
- Cada, L. F., Jr. (2022). ENTREPRENEURSHIP POTENTIALS AMONG SELECTED FILIPINO PROFESSIONALS. *Global Conference on Business and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.35912/gcbm.v1i1.16>
- Cardon, M. S., & Murnieks, C. Y. (2020). The profits and perils of passion in entrepreneurship. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788973403>
- Cardon, M. S., Glauser, M., & Murnieks, C. Y. (2017). Passion for what? Expanding the domains of entrepreneurial passion. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 8, 24–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbvi.2017.05.004>
- Cardon, M. S., Grégoire, D. A., Stevens, C. E., & Patel, P. C. (2013). Measuring entrepreneurial passion: Conceptual foundations and scale validation. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 28(3), 373–396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2012.03.003>
- Choiriyah, C., Fatimah, F., Agustina, S., & Ulfa, U. (2021). The effect of return on assets, return on equity, net profit margin, earning per share, and operating profit margin on stock prices of banking companies in Indonesia Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Finance Research*, 1(2), 103–123. <https://doi.org/10.47747/ijfr.v1i2.280>
- Demir, S. (2022). Comparison of Normality Tests in Terms of Sample Sizes under Different Skewness and Kurtosis Coefficients. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 9(2), 397–409. <https://doi.org/10.21449/ijate.1101295>
- Department of Agriculture. (2017). 2017-2022 Philippine Industry Roadmap. <https://www.da.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Philippine-Coffee-Industry-Roadmap-2017-2022.pdf>
- Duckett, L. J. (2021). Quantitative research excellence: study design and reliable and valid measurement of variables. *Journal of Human Lactation*, 37(3), 456–463. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08903344211019285>
- Ewing Marion Kauffman Foundation. (2019). EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT OF BUSINESS OWNERS IN THE UNITED STATES. *Trends in Entrepreneurship Series*, 2. https://www.kauffman.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Kauffman_Education_Attainment_2020_final.pdf
- Feng, B., & Chen, M. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurial passion on psychology and behavior of entrepreneurs. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01733>
- Fox, S. (2024, September 11). How to determine survey sample size: A short guide. *Survicate*. <https://survicate.com/blog/survey-sample-size/#:~:text=Many%20statisticians%20concur>
- Francisco, J. P. (2023). Bricolage and the Entrepreneurial Process in Times of Crisis: Insights from New Ventures in an Emerging Economy. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4440244>
- Handayani, N., & Winarningsih, S. (2020). The effect of net profit margin and return on equity toward profit growth. *Moneter - Jurnal*

Akuntansi Dan Keuangan, 7(2), 198–204. <https://doi.org/10.31294/moneter.v7i2.8701>

Hansson, E., & Weiss, M. L. (2023). Routledge Handbook of Civil and Uncivil Society in Southeast Asia. In Routledge eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780367422080>

Hernisa, J., Mahagangga, I. G. A. O., & Sastrawan, I. G. A. (2023). The Phenomenon of the Rise of Coffee Shops after the Pandemic on Leisure and Recreation Activities in the Renon Area (Case of SAGA Coffee Visitor Motivation). *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 4(8), 2239–2247. <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V4ISSUE8/IJRPR16349.pdf>

Huss, S. (2020). The impact of an entrepreneur's age on entrepreneurial passion : an explanatory study. <https://essay.utwente.nl/81853/>

Kadiyono, A., Sulistiobudi, R., & Zuhijah, A. (2019). Why College Students Have Big Motivation to Start Their Own Business, but Not Continuing The Business After Graduate? *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 197, 54–61. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/bcm-18/125910914>

Kaya, S. (2020). The factors predicting students' participation in online English courses. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 21(91). <https://doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2021.91.14>

Kişi, N. (2020). Portfolio entrepreneurship and strategic decision making in the global context. In *Advances in business strategy and competitive advantage book series* (pp. 315–331). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-1981-3.ch015>

Kozlinska, I. & Aston University. (2016, December 22). Entrepreneurial experiences “no better than textbooks,” says study. *Physics.org*. https://phys.org/news/2016-12-entrepreneurial-textbooks.html#google_vignette

Kumari, K. T. (2023). The Impact of Entrepreneurial Passion on the Entrepreneurial Performance in MSME's At Kollam District In Kerala [Presidency University]. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/>

Kusa, N. D., & Danladi, N. Y. (2024). Entrepreneurial passion on the success of SME's in Plateau State, Nigeria: The role of entrepreneurial skills. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism and Entrepreneurship*, 5(1), 57–74. <https://doi.org/10.35912/joste.v5i1.2124>

Lee, Y., & Herrmann, P. (2019). View of Entrepreneurial passion: A systematic review and research opportunities. *Journal of Small Business Strategy*. <https://libjournals.mtsu.edu/index.php/jsbs/article/view/1678/1262>

Lee, Y., Cortes, A. F., & Joo, M. (2021). Entrepreneurship education and founding passion: The moderating role of entrepreneurial family background. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.743672>

Luu, N., & Nguyen, H. (2020). Entrepreneurial passion and a firm's innovation strategies. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 59(4), 794–818. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00472778.2020.1729026>

Malaluan, A. Q. (2019). Performance of micro and small enterprises in the Philippine setting. *Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(1), p15. <https://doi.org/10.30560/jems.v2n1p15>

Mayoshe, B., & Nuringsih, K. (2021). Understanding entrepreneurial passion among new entrepreneurs. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research/Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210805.040>

Mendoza, X. L. D., & Tadeo, J. B. (2023). Analysis of micro, small, medium enterprises: The cases of Singapore, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand and Vietnam. *Journal of Management, Economics, and Industrial Organization*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.31039/jomeino.2023.7.1.1>

Mohajan, H. K. (2020). Quantitative Research: a successful investigation in natural and social sciences. *Journal of Economic Development Environment and People*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.26458/jedep.v9i4.679>

Msosa, S. K. (2023). Impact of socio-demographic variables on entrepreneurship intention in the Higher Education sector. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147-4478), 12(2), 422–428. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v12i2.2395>

Munro, O. (2024, July 16). What is a Good Profit Margin? Industry Averages & How to Improve. *Unleashed*. <https://www.unleashedsoftware.com/>

Nariswari, T. N., & Nugraha, N. M. (2020). Profit growth : impact of net profit margin, gross profit margin and total assests turnover. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies* (2147-4486), 9(4), 87–96. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijfbs.v9i4.937>

Neal, J. (2020). Entrepreneurial passion: The difference between expert and novice entrepreneurs in the United States. <https://essay.utwente.nl/81946/>

Newman, A., Obschonka, M., Moeller, J., & Chandan, G. G. (2019). Entrepreneurial Passion: A review, synthesis, and agenda for future research. *Applied Psychology*, 70(2), 816–860. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12236>

Nurhasanah, S., & Dewi, C. (2020). THE EMERGENCE OF LOCAL COFFEE SHOPS IN INDONESIA AS A COUNTER TO

AMERICAN CULTURE HEGEMONY. *Rubikon*, 6(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.22146/rubikon.v6i1.61485>

Ogundana, O. M., Simba, A., Dana, L., & Liguori, E. (2021). Women entrepreneurship in developing economies: A gender-based growth model. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 59(sup1), S42–S72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0047278.2021.1938098>

Okoye, K., & Hosseini, S. (2024a). Correlation Tests in R: Pearson Cor, Kendall’s Tau, and Spearman’s Rho. In *R Programming* (pp. 247–277). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-3385-9_12

Okoye, K., & Hosseini, S. (2024b). Mann–Whitney U Test and Kruskal–Wallis H Test Statistics in R. In *R Programming* (pp. 225–246). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-3385-9_11

Parker, T., James, M., & Kvilhaug, S. (2024, June 19). What’s a good profit margin for a new business? Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/personal-finance/093015/whats-good-profit-marg-in-new-business.asp>

Saif, H. A., & Ghania, U. (2019). NEED FOR ACHIEVEMENT AS a PREDICTOR OF ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOR: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL PASSION FOR FOUNDING AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INTEREST. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 10(1), 40–53. <https://doi.org/10.32479/irmm.8949>

Sarasvathy, S. D. (2008). Effectuation: elements of entrepreneurial expertise. https://cdm.epfl.ch/files/content/sites/mtei/files/shared/mtei_seminars/2008/saravsathy_book_101108.pdf

Siebert, M. (2024). *Franchise your business: The Guide to Employing the Greatest Growth Strategy Ever*. Entrepreneur Press.

Schulte-Holthaus, S., & Kuckertz, A. (2023). How life context affects entrepreneurs’ passion and performance. *Review of Managerial Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-023-00643-y>

Simon, R., & Suarez, M. T. (2022). Examining the Behavioral Intention of Philippine MSMEs Toward Business Intelligence Adoption. *Journal of Business and Management*, 28(1), 67–99. <https://doi.org/10.1504/jbm.2022.141295>

Solomon, S. J., & Mathias, B. D. (2020). The artisans’ dilemma: Artisan entrepreneurship and the challenge of firm growth. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 35(5), 106044. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2020.10604>

Tampon, V. (2023, July 29). Coffee statistics you need to know for 2024 and beyond. <https://hillsandvalleys.ph/coffee-statistics-philippines/>

Teixeira, L. (2020). The consumption of experiences in specialty coffee shops. In *Elsevier eBooks* (pp. 275–295). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-814721-4.00010-x>

Tenorio-Mandane, M. G. B. (2020). Entrepreneurial Characteristics on the Growth of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. *Asia Pacific Journal of Academic Research in Social Sciences*, 5(2), 52–66. <https://research.lpubatangas.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/APJARSS-2020-5-005.pdf>

Tugade, L. O. (2020). Re-creating farms into Agritourism: Cases of selected micro-entrepreneurs in the Philippines. *DOAJ (DOAJ: Directory of Open Access Journals)*. <https://doaj.org/article/0728409d06714b0ab009d5a0357b7a95>

Vesalainen, J., & Pihkala, T. (2000). Entrepreneurial identity, intentions and the effect of the push-factor. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 4(2). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/308416709_Entrepreneurial_identity_intention_s_and_the_effect_of_the_push-factor

Victor, A. A., Monica, M., & Danie, A. (2023). Effect of financing structure on the profitability of micro and small enterprises in Nakuru Central Business District. *Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669821>

Walsh, G. S., & Cunningham, J. A. (2023). Business failure and entrepreneur experiences of passion. *International Small Business Journal Researching Entrepreneurship*, 42(3), 283–307. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02662426231194482>

Widani, M. A., Perkasa, I. G. T. D., Widiasih, N. L. P. S., & Yasa, N. N. K. (2022). Business Development Strategy in PT. Revolver Love Coffee, Badung Regency, Bali: based on SWOT analysis. *Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6685217>

Wiltbank, R., Dew, N., Read, S., & Sarasvathy, S. D. (2009). “Effectual Versus Predictive Logics in Entrepreneurial Decision-Making: Differences between Experts and Novices.” *SSRN Electronic Journal*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1428867

Xiao, Y., Dowejko, M. K., Au, K., & Hsu, A. J. C. (2019). “Jack-of-all-trades” with passion: Keener to pursue startup in a team? *Journal of Small Business Management*, 58(4), 806–833. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00472778.2019.1672708>

Yang, L., & Zhang, Y. (2020). Digital financial Inclusion and Sustainable growth of small and micro Enterprises—Evidence based on China’s new third board market listed companies. *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3733. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093733>

Yeh, C., Lin, H., Wang, Y., Wang, Y., & Lo, C. (2021). Investigating the relationships between entrepreneurial education and self-efficacy and performance in the context of internet entrepreneurship. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 19(3), 100565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2021.100565>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jason Rick T. Suanes

Rizal Technological University – Philippines

Merry Rose R. Reyes

Rizal Technological University – Philippines

Trizie Anne R. Romasanta

Rizal Technological University – Philippines

Sharmaine H. Matamorosa

Rizal Technological University – Philippines

Joaqin Clemente R. Permejo

Rizal Technological University – Philippines